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SPECIAL RISK CHARACTERISTICS OF DROPOUTS REGARDING THE DROPOUT INTENTION OF BACHELOR STUDENTS IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical engineering programs in Germany are characterized by high dropout rates of 34% in the study entry phase [1]. These persistently high dropout rates can be attributed to a number of performance-related problems of students in the study entry phase [2]. Other reasons for dropout include unsatisfactory entry qualifications in mathematics and physics [3], and lack of motivation to study [4]. Based on the dropout model of Heublein (2017) [5], this paper identifies subject-specific reasons for academic success and dropout in the bachelor's program in mechanical engineering in order to improve the study conditions in an evidence-based manner depending on the specific characteristics of the students and the specific qualification goals.

1 INTRODUCTION

In Heublein's (2017) dropout model (Fig. 1), dropout is depicted as a complex multicausal process that can be divided into the phases of preliminary phase of the study programme, current study situation, and decision. In the preliminary phase of the study programme, individuals are socialized in such a way that they acquire the higher education entrance qualification (HZB) and subsequently decide on a course of study and on a university. Matriculation marks the beginning of the individual study process, which is characterized by the interaction of internal factors (study behavior, study motivation, psychological and physical resources, and performance in the studies) and external factors (type of university with its respective study conditions). If discrepancies between the internal and external factors do not resolve, the decision to drop out becomes more likely. Educational origin and migration background as well as personality influence socialization in the education process, study decisions and the individual study process.

Fig. 1. dropout model according to Heublein (2017) [5].

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Instruments

In addition to the educational origin and the migration background as operationalization of the origin from the dropout model according to Heublein (2017), the educational socialization at the beginning of the first semester was recorded with the help of a questionnaire on the sociodemographic background [6]. For this purpose, the type of HZB incl. grade as well as information on vocational training were asked. In addition, the students indicated whether they had taken a basic or advanced course or no course in physics or mathematics in the upper secondary

school. The subject-related study prerequisites associated with educational socialization were surveyed using written performance tests to record previous knowledge in mathematics and engineering mechanics [7]. Additional performance tests in mathematics and engineering mechanics [7] were used at the end of first and second semester to survey special knowledge acquisition as a component of study performance. The tests were scaled using the 1-PL IRT model (Rasch model).

The cognitive abilities (subscale Figural Reasoning) [8] were also surveyed. Furthermore, online surveys were repeatedly administered in the middle of the first subject semester (MZP2), end of the first subject semester (MZP3), beginning of the second subject semester (MZP4), end of the second subject semester (MZP5), beginning of the third subject semester (MZP6), end of the third semester (MZP7) and beginning of the fourth semester (MZP8). In the online surveys were the individual motivation to drop out [9, 10], study behavior through resource management [11], psychological and physical resources [12], and study motivation [13, 14, 15] surveyed. The choice of study program or type of university results directly from the sample and was therefore not asked separately.

Since this paper focuses on the analysis of students with academic success (active students) and dropouts (inactive students), the surveyed sample is divided into two groups based on the response options of the item "Are you still studying the subject in which you are participating in this study?". The item could be answered as follows: 1: "Yes, I am still actively studying this subject.", 2: "No, I am no longer actively studying this subject, but I am still enrolled.", 3: "No, I am studying another subject.", 4: "No, I have exmatriculated." It was used within the online survey at the above measurement time points. Active students answered the item with answer choice 1 at least until the beginning of the third semester of study. Inactive students answered the item with answer choice 2, 3, or 4 during the survey period from the middle of the first semester to the beginning of the fourth semester.

3 RESULTS

The presentation of results first shows to what extent active students and inactive students differ with regard to the characteristics that shape the preliminary study phase. Furthermore, results on the relevant characteristics of the individual study process and the individual intention to drop out are presented.

The sample ($N_{\text{total}} = 145$, $N_{\text{active}} = 100$, $N_{\text{inactive}} = 45$) consists of students who started studying mechanical engineering at two universities and two universities of applied sciences in Germany in the winter semester 2018/2019. From a χ^2 homogeneity test, the proportions of active students (69.0%) and inactive students (31.0%) are the same at universities as well as at universities of applied sciences. Due to low case numbers, no analyses were performed separately by type of higher education institution (university and university of applied sciences).

3.1 Preliminary phase of the study programme

From a χ^2 -homogeneity test, active students ($N_{\text{active}} = 100$, 25.0% female and 75.0% male) and inactive students ($N_{\text{inactive}} = 32$, 31.3% female and 68.8% male) do not differ in gender distribution ($\chi^2(1) = 0.491$, $p = .483$). Descriptive examination of the data reveals an age average of 19.0 years for active students ($N_{\text{active}} = 100$) and an age average of 20.3 years for inactive students ($N_{\text{inactive}} = 44$); both groups of students do not differ significantly from each other in age average ($t(142) = 0.993$, $p = .322$).

The factors belonging to socialization in the education process are presented below. In the type of acquisition of the HZB, no significant differences in the distribution between the active students and inactive students can be observed ($N_{\text{active}} = 93/N_{\text{inactive}} = 42$, $\chi^2(2) = 2.905$, $p = .234$). While 72.0% of the active students acquired their HZB at a Gymnasium, 59.5% of the inactive students' HZB acquisition falls on at a Gymnasium. Their HZB at a comprehensive school has 16.1% among active students and 28.6% among inactive students. The remaining students of both groups of students have the HZB from a vocational college, the HZB as a second educational pathway, or other. No significant differences become apparent in the taking of physics as a school subject in the upper school. For the active students, there is almost a 40/30 distribution with respect to the choice of a basic course or an advanced course, and for the inactive students a 50/10 distribution. Another part of both groups of students did not take physics at all in high school. In contrast, significant differences can be found in the use of mathematics as a subject. Active students take this subject 20.8% as a basic course and 79.2% as an advanced course. Inactive students, on the other hand, take this subject 51.2% as a basic course and 48.8% as an advanced course ($N_{\text{active}} = 96/N_{\text{inactive}} = 41$, $\chi^2(1) = 12.649$, $p = .000$, Cramer $V = .304$). From the total cohort of active students, 17.3% students have completed education prior to entering the program, and among inactive students, 13.3% have completed education prior to entering the program; both student groups do not differ significantly with respect to having completed education prior to entering the program ($N_{\text{active}} = 98/N_{\text{inactive}} = 44$, $\chi^2(1) = .368$, $p = .544$). The active students surveyed achieved a 2.11 as their average HZB grade. Inactive students achieved a significantly worse average HZB grade of 2.44 ($N_{\text{active}} = 100/N_{\text{inactive}} = 43$, $t(141) = 3.160$, $p = .002$, Cohen's $d = .581$). Active students and inactive students also enter the mechanical engineering program with strongly different mean person abilities in prior knowledge (total) ($N_{\text{active}} = 95/N_{\text{inactive}} = 43$, $t(136) = -5.903$, $p = .000$, Cohen's $d = .613$) (Fig. 3). A detailed examination of the person ability of prior knowledge of both groups of students shows lower prior knowledge for the inactive students than for the active students in both mathematics and engineering mechanics. The reported differences are statistically significant in mathematical prior knowledge ($N_{\text{active}} = 95/N_{\text{inactive}} = 43$, $t(136) = -4.599$, $p = .000$, Cohen's $d = .985$) and in prior knowledge in engineering mechanics ($N_{\text{active}} = 95/N_{\text{inactive}} = 43$, $t(136) = -5.129$, $p = .000$, Cohen's $d = .598$), so that one can speak of

different subject-specific study prerequisites for active students and inactive students.

Fig. 2. error bars of average person ability for the performance test of previous knowledge (total, mathematics, engineering mechanics) at the beginning of the first semester of study for active students and inactive students.

The characterization of the educational origin is done by a five-level classification according to the concept of educational origin of the DZHW [16]. Here, the characteristics of the professional education of the father and mother of the students are divided into the following gradations: very low (neither parent has a professional - non-academic - degree), low (one parent has a professional - non-academic - degree), medium (both parents have a professional - non-academic - degree), high (one parent has an academic degree) and very high (both parents have an academic degree). The breakdown by educational origin shows significant differences in the distribution of active students and inactive students ($N_{\text{active}} = 100/N_{\text{inactive}} = 45$, $\chi^2(4) = 13.588$, $p = .009$, Cramer-V = .306). The active students show a split of 2.0%, 6.0%, 44.0%, 23.0%, and 25.0% in the different categories (very low/low/medium/high). Inactive students show a breakdown of 11.1%, 20.0%, 37.8%, 15.6%, and 15.6% in the different categories. Active students are significantly more likely than inactive students to come from academic families.

Migration background is also considered as an operationalization of origin. The breakdown by migration background also shows significant differences in the distribution of active students and inactive students ($N_{\text{active}} = 97/N_{\text{inactive}} = 40$, $\chi^2(1) = 15.826$, $p = .000$, Cramer-V = .340). Of active students, 3.1% have an immigrant

background. Among inactive students, the proportion of students with a migration background (25.0%) is significantly higher.

3.2 Decision

In the following, the average intention of active and inactive students to drop out of the study program from the middle of the first semester to the beginning of the fourth semester is examined in more detail (Fig. 3). During the survey period under consideration, there are significant differences in the average intention to drop out between active and inactive students (MZP2: $N_{\text{active}} = 90/N_{\text{inactive}} = 35$, $t(123) = 8.418$, $p = .000$, MZP3: $N_{\text{active}} = 94/N_{\text{inactive}} = 32$, $t(124) = 10.185$, $p = .000$, MZP4: $N_{\text{active}} = 94/N_{\text{inactive}} = 31$, $t(123) = 9.313$, $p = .000$, MZP6: $N_{\text{active}} = 75/N_{\text{inactive}} = 20$, $t(93) = 9.367$, $p = .000$, MZP7: $N_{\text{active}} = 84/N_{\text{inactive}} = 8$, $t(90) = 5.448$, $p = .000$, MZP9: $N_{\text{active}} = 73/N_{\text{inactive}} = 9$, $t(80) = 4.733$, $p = .000$, MZP10: $N_{\text{active}} = 72/N_{\text{inactive}} = 12$, $t(82) = 5.438$, $p = .000$). It can be seen that active students tend to report a low average intention to drop out over the entire survey period, which increases slightly over the course of their studies. The average intention to drop out among inactive students is more than twice as high as among active students over the entire survey period. Among inactive students, the mean intention to drop out of the study program increases more strongly until the end of the second semester, after which the average intention to drop out of the study program decreases slightly.

Fig. 3. error bars of average intention to drop out of active students and inactive students at different measurement time points.

3.3 Current study situation

In a further step, a regression analysis is calculated for active students and inactive students respectively in order to investigate the influence of the factors of the individual study process on individual dropout intention at the beginning of the second semester (Fig. 4). The regression analyses show that there is no significant influence of study behavior or psych./phys. resources on individual dropout intention at the beginning of the second semester. For active students, high study motivation causes low individual dropout intention ($\beta_{\text{active}} = -.194^*$). Inactive students show no influence of study motivation on individual dropout intention. In this group of students, however, study performance shows an influence on individual dropout intention ($\beta_{\text{inactive}} = -.382^*$). The factor study performance in the regression model includes prior knowledge in mathematics, because for analyses of the influence of the factor expertise on the individual intention to drop out of the study, the number of subjects of the inactive students is not sufficient.

Fig. 4. regression model for the influence of the factors of the individual study process on the intention to drop out at the beginning of the second semester.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Several differences between inactive students and active students can already be identified in preliminary phase of the study programme. In addition to a lower HZB grade, inactive students have less prior knowledge of mathematics and engineering mechanics. There are also differences between the two groups of students in terms of their educational background and migration background. Inactive students have a lower educational background than active students and are more likely to have a migration background. During the individual study process, inactive students show a correlation between prior mathematical knowledge and individual intention to drop out. For this group of students, a low level of prior mathematical knowledge leads to a high individual intention to drop out.

For active students, there is no correlation between performance-related factors and the individual intention to drop out. However, for this group of students, a low motivation to study causes an increased individual intention to drop out. The reduction of individual dropout intentions can be achieved by supporting first-year students in compensating for deficits in prior knowledge in mathematics, ideally before they start their studies.

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